

INTERSTATE AND GENDER DISPARITIES IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM IN INDIA

Vivek Kumar Mishra¹

Junior Research fellow
Department of Economics,
University of Allahabad,
Allahabad, (India)

Dr. Alka Mishra

Guest Faculty
Department of Economics,
Jagat Taran Girls Degree College,
University of Allahabad,
Allahabad, (India)

Abstract

In this paper attempts have been made to explore the current status of higher education in India and to examine the status of gender parity in the higher education in India. The analysis is based on the secondary data collected from the report of All India survey of Higher Education. The study is descriptive in its nature and discusses various issues related to the higher education system in India. Simple tools of analysis like tables, charts and graphs have been utilized to present the information in a convenient way. The paper reveals that there is interstate disparities in terms of college density, average enrolment, gross enrolment ratio, gender parity index etc. the issues related to inclusion of women in the higher education have not been taken care properly. The paper concludes with the remarks that the importance of education in the life of a person and in nation building is beyond any dispute. The education does not only make a man perfect by enriching his thoughts and process of thinking, it contributes to the growth of a nation also. Focus should be on women's education because the knowledge and empowerment of one woman can bring about a change in a family and even the society as a whole. Hence the participation or inclusion of women in education is of grave importance from the point of view of society and nation as well.

Keywords: College Density, Gender disparity. Gross enrolment ratio, Higher Education, Interstate, India.

I. Introduction

The higher education does not just provide educated persons for knowledge economy; it enriches them with professional, technical and managerial skills. Hence the role of higher education is instrumental in the process of modernization and development of an economy. It has been observed worldwide that leading countries are putting emphasis to develop knowledge based industries. The system attracts the youth and attempts to find out and utilize the the talent hidden in the inner soul. It delineates to improve learning and teaching throughout the process of education. Vital role in the regional initiatives are also being carried out by higher education institutions. It disseminates the process of technology transfer and R&D activities all around the world, leading to enhanced technology infrastructure. In short the higher education converts the traditional economy into the knowledge economy, bringing positive changes in all the sectors of the same. Since independence India has experienced considerable improvement in the level and structure of higher education system. Today higher education system in India is the largest in the world in terms of institutions and second largest in terms of enrolments. The higher education system in India has included the objective of nation building as the core of its functioning.

Besides being the second most populous country (with 17.5 % of world population), India is one of the youngest countries in the world also, strengthened with nearly 47% of the population under the age group of 0to24 years.

¹ Corresponding Author,

This young population may contribute to the economy if it could be converted into human resource with the help of good health and education accompanied with required skills. India has one of the largest and complex education systems in the world, which incorporates about 1.5 million institutes and around 250 million enrolments. Under the umbrella of higher education there are 717 Universities, 36812 Colleges and 11565 Stand Alone Institutions in the country. Out of them 229 University are privately managed. There are 42 Central University, 1 Central and 13 State Open University, 68 Institute of National Importance, 309 State Public University, 5 Institute under State Legislature Act, 36 Deemed University Government, 11 Deemed University Government Aided and 3 Others University².

II. Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are twofold:

- To explore the current status of higher education system in India.
- To examine the interstate and gender disparities in the higher education system in India.

III. Methodology of the Research

To achieve the objectives of the study information related to various key parameters related to higher education have been collected from various trustworthy sources especially from the All India Survey of Higher Education. The study is descriptive in its nature and discusses various issues related to the structure and performance of higher education system in India. Simple tools of analysis like tables, charts and graphs have been utilized to present the information in a convenient way.

IV. Analysis

The Higher education system can be segmented into Central Universities, State Universities, Deemed Universities and Open Universities, further except the Central Universities the remaining can be classified in to the Government owned, Government aided and Private. Besides the universities and colleges there are several institutions of national importance and under state legislation. The state wise distribution of the same has been illustrated in the Table 1. Most of the universities (309) are being governed by state governments, followed by state private universities (149). Uttar Pradesh and Rajasthan has the highest number of universities in India followed by Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra and Karnataka. These five states cover 37.5 % of the universities.

Almost every state has at least one central university except Andhra Pradesh, Chandigarh and Goa with no central university. While Delhi and Uttar Pradesh are being benefitted with 4 universities running in each followed by Telangana where 3 central universities are functional. In UTs of Andaman & Nicobar Island, Dadra & Nagar Haveli, Daman & Diu and Lakshadweep, there is no University.

² AISHE 2013-14 report (Provisional)

Figure 1: Sate wise and Type wise Number of Universities

Author's illustration, Data Source: AISHE 2013-14 (P)

*CU=Central University, CO= Central Open University, INI=Institute of National Importance O=Others, SPU=State Public University ISLA=Institute under State Legislature Act, SOU= State Open University, SPvU= State Private University, DUG= Deemed University Government, DUGA= Deemed University-Government Aided DUP= Deemed University-Private .

4.1 College, College Density & Average Enrolment:

It is evident from the Table 1 that Uttar Pradesh Maharashtra, Karnataka, Rajasthan and Andhra Pradesh has highest number of colleges in India. However if we consider the college density as number of colleges per lakh of population (in Age group 18-23 years) Puducherry has the highest college density followed by Telangana, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Himachal Pradesh. Lakshadweep, Bihar, Jharkhand, Delhi and West Bengal have shown worst performance in terms of college density. In terms of average enrolment per collage Bihar, Jharkhand, Chandigarh, West Bengal and Arunachal Pradesh are the highest performers in the group. Lakshadweep, Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Daman & Diu, Nagaland and Karnataka have registered lowest average enrolment per college.

Table 1: College, College Density & Average Enrolment

	STATES/UTs	No. of College	College per lakh population	Average Enrolment per College
1	Andaman & Nicobar Islands	6	13	356
2	Andhra Pradesh	2559	45	524
3	Arunachal Pradesh	26	16	1513
4	Assam	535	15	941
5	Bihar	694	6	2142
6	Chandigarh	27	17	1682
7	Chhatisgarh	652	21	522
8	Dadra & Nagar Haveli	7	13	645
9	Daman & Diu	6	12	395
10	Delhi	186	9	1451
11	Goa	55	34	582
12	Gujarat	1943	27	627
13	Haryana	1088	34	729
14	Himachal Pradesh	296	39	537
15	Jammu and Kashmir	332	24	872
16	Jharkhand	269	7	2072
17	Karnataka	3281	45	442
18	Kerala	1125	36	603
19	Lakshadweep	0	0	0
20	Madhya Pradesh	2312	27	589
21	Maharashtra	4689	35	531
22	Manipur	83	28	1199
23	Meghalaya	62	18	990
24	Mizoram	29	22	645
25	Nagaland	61	24	430
26	Odisha	1124	24	629
27	Puducherry	84	60	559
28	Punjab	966	29	820
29	Rajasthan	2733	32	734

30	Sikkim	12	15	520
31	Tamil Nadu	2522	33	816
32	Telangana	2272	55	597
33	Tripura	46	10	1029
34	Uttar Pradesh	5349	22	1171
35	Uttrakhand	398	32	863
36	West Bengal	983	9	1542
	All India	36812	26	752

Source: AISHE, 2013-14 (p)

4.2 State wise and Sector wise Distribution of Colleges:

It has been observed by AISHE that 75% of Colleges running in India are privately managed out of which 60% of colleges are Private-Unaided and 15% Private Aided, remaining 25 % colleges are running under government sector. Andhra Pradesh and Telangana has more than 83% Private-Unaided Colleges, whereas, Mizoram has only 3%, Chandigarh has 4% and Bihar and Assam has only 8% Private-Unaided Colleges.

Figure 2: Distribution of Colleges

Author’s illustration, Data Source: AISHE 2013-14 (P)

Table 2: State wise and sector wise Distribution of colleges:

State	Private Un-Aided	Private Aided	Total Private	Government	Total
Andaman & Nicobar Islands				4	4
Andhra Pradesh	1303	120	1423	139	1562
Arunachal Pradesh	3	3	6	9	15

Assam	29	9	38	328	366
Bihar	45	36	81	452	533
Chandigarh	1	7	8	16	24
Chhatisgarh	273	63	336	294	630
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	3	1	4	2	6
Daman & Diu	3	1	4	2	6
Delhi	59	13	72	86	158
Goa	10	20	30	20	50
Gujarat	870	475	1345	476	1821
Haryana	433	98	531	149	680
Himachal Pradesh	118	14	132	122	254
Jammu and Kashmir	102	10	112	107	219
Jharkhand	44	16	60	115	175
Karnataka	2037	405	2442	604	3046
Kerala	456	189	645	151	796
Madhya Pradesh	1010	190	1200	555	1755
Maharashtra	2639	883	3522	769	4291
Manipur	20	14	34	48	82
Meghalaya	11	12	23	14	37
Mizoram	1		1	28	29
Nagaland	7	32	39	21	60
Odisha	189	364	553	286	839
Puducherry	46	2	48	24	72
Punjab	248	82	330	105	435
Rajasthan	793	47	840	283	1123
Sikkim	5		5	7	12
Tamil Nadu	1885	256	2141	335	2476
Telangana	1147	95	1242	143	1385
Tripura	4	2	6	39	45
Uttar Pradesh	2050	410	2460	544	3004
Uttrakhand	88	48	136	95	231
West Bengal	340	201	541	396	937
All India	16272	4118	20390	6768	27158

Source: AISHE 2013-14 (P)

On the basis of true responses received from 27158 colleges out of 36812 colleges in India, the AISHE observed that Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh have the largest no. of private colleges while the government colleges are ample in Gujarat, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, and Maharashtra. The higher education system in terms of number of colleges in Bihar, Tripura, Assam, Mizoram and Andaman & Nicobar Islands has been dominated by government sector where as in Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra and Uttar Pradesh have been benefitted by growth of private sector where private sector

shares 91% to 82 % of total number of colleges. According to AISHE Andhra Pradesh, Telangana and Tamil Nadu has more than 75 % private un-aided colleges in their territory, whereas Tripura, Bihar, Assam, Chandigarh, and Mizoram has less than 10 % of private un-aided colleges. Andaman & Nicobar Islands does not have any private un-aided or aided college.

4.3 Gender parity in Higher Education:

The importance of education in the life of a person and in nation building is beyond any dispute. A person becomes perfect with education as he is not only gaining something from it, but also contributing to the growth of a nation. Focus should be on women's education because the knowledge and empowerment of one woman can bring about a change in a family and even the society as a whole (The Hindu)³. Hence the participation or inclusion of women in education is of grave importance from the point of view of society and nation as well. The enrolment scenario in different courses and the condition of gender parity has been discussed in this section.

Table 3: Course wise Enrolment & Female Enrolment Ratio

Course	Course wise Enrolment			*Female Enrolment Ratio
	Male	Female	Total	
Ph.D.	64977	44548	109525	0.685596
M.Phil.	13314	17168	30482	1.28947
Post Graduate	1860332	1848109	3708441	0.99343
Under Graduate	13628070	11675318	25303388	0.856711
PG Diploma	148222	120301	268523	0.811627
Diploma	1500323	609383	2109706	0.406168
Certificate	86277	97437	183714	1.129351
Integrated	69388	41818	111206	0.602669
Grand Total All Courses	17370903	14454082	31824985	0.832086

Source: AISHE 2013-14 (P) * Author's calculation

The state wise enrolment at various levels of education reveals that among all courses the condition of female's participation or gender parity is highest in case of M.Phil. and certificate courses. The participation of females in diploma courses cannot be regarded satisfactory as it scores only .40 at Female Enrolment Ratio. The same condition has been followed by the female enrolment in Integrated and Ph.D. courses. Here the Female Enrolment Ratio has been calculated as the ratio of female enrolment and male enrolment in the corresponding group. The Female Enrolment Ratio for all courses together comes to be 0.83, which should be unity, indicating that we have to follow a long journey yet to achieve the parity. Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in Higher Education in India is 22.6, which is calculated for 18-23 years of age group. GER for male population is 23.7 and female it is 21.4. For Scheduled Castes, it is 17.4 and for Scheduled Tribes, it is 12% as compared to the national GER of 22.6 (AISHE 2013-14).

³ <http://www.thehindu.com/features/kids/importance-of-education/article4619651.ece>

Figure 3: Gender Parity Index

Author's illustration, Data Source: AISHE 2013-14 (P)

The state wise gender parity index has been illustrated in the figure 3. One could observed from the figure that on an average in India the gender parity index (based on gross enrolment of male and females in higher education between the age group of 18 – 23 years) is .90, which reveals that there are in general 10% inclination in favour of male enrolment. States like Lakshdweep, Goa, Daman & Diu, Chandigarh and Kerala are having gender parity index better than all India average. Whereas, the condition of females in terms of enrolments are unsatisfactory in the states like Tripura, Rajasthan and Madhya Pradesh.

V. Conclusions and Suggestions:

In this paper attempts have been made to explore the current scenario of higher education in India and to delineate the current status of gender parity in the higher education in India. The analysis is based on the secondary data collected from the report of All India survey of Higher Education 2013-14. To achieve the objectives of the study paper utilizes simple tools of analysis like tabulation, charts and graphs. It has been observed by AISHE that 75% of Colleges running in India are privately managed out of which 60% of colleges are Private-Unaided and 15% Private Aided, remaining 25 % colleges are running under government sector. Andhra Pradesh and Telangana has more than 83% Private-Unaided Colleges, whereas, Mizoram has only 3%, Chandigarh has 4% and Bihar and Assam has only 8% Private-Unaided Colleges. Except M.Phil. and Certificate courses the females are far behind their male counterpart in terms of enrolment ratio. As revealed by the Gender Equity Index, the condition of female enrolment across the states is uneven also, on the one hand there are states like Lakshadweep and Goa where the index exceeds the unity and on the other hand there are states like Tripura and Rajasthan where the index is far below the national average (0.90).

The paper reveals that there is interstate disparities in terms of college density, average enrolment, gross enrolment ratio, gender parity index etc. the issues related to inclusion of women in the higher education have not been taken care properly. The paper concludes with the remarks that the importance of education in the life of a person and in nation building is beyond any dispute. The education does not only make a man perfect by enriching his thoughts and process of thinking, it contributes to the growth of a nation also. Focus should be on women's education because the knowledge and empowerment of one woman can bring about a change in a family and even the

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